

StegoCrypt: Multi-Image LSB Steganography with AES–GCM and AES–CTR Permutation

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Steganography complements cryptography by concealing information in benign media [4, 6]. Although least–significant–bit (LSB) methods are practical, predictable write patterns and missing integrity checks can enable forensic detection or silent corruption [4, 6]. **StegoCrypt** is a browser-only, offline-first system that combines bit-plane LSB embedding with a pseudorandom permutation of pixel/channel indices and authenticated encryption, providing confidentiality and integrity while keeping all processing local. A strict Content Security Policy (self-hosted scripts only; no network connections) and explicit revocation of object URLs help confine data to the local session.

The system supports up to eight concurrent payloads, one per bit-plane (0...7), each protected by an independent passphrase. A fresh 16-byte salt and 10^5 PBKDF2–SHA256 iterations derive the AES–GCM key material [2, 5]. Separately, the deterministic PRNG that drives index shuffling uses AES–CTR keyed with SHA–256(passphrase) and a 128-bit counter [3, 7] (CTR is used **only** for permutation; payloads are encrypted exclusively with AES–GCM [2]). Each embedded payload is packed as salt||IV||CT (12-byte IV, 128-bit tag) and preceded by a 4-byte length header, enabling stateless decryption and reducing parsing ambiguity [2, 5].

For a cover of size $W \times H$ with $C = 3$ channels (RGB; alpha excluded), a single bit-plane exposes $N = W \times H \times C$ LSB slots; nominal capacity per plane is $\lfloor N/8 \rfloor$ bytes minus the 4-byte header [4]. Pixel/channel indices are enumerated over RGB only and shuffled in place via Fisher–Yates [1]; ciphertext bits are then embedded following that order to reduce obvious regularities [4, 6]. Embedding and extraction run in $\mathcal{O}(N)$ time with a single pass over the pixel buffer. The implementation uses HTML5 Canvas `ImageData.data` (`Uint8ClampedArray`) for pixels and a `Uint32Array` index map.

Figure 1 shows the client-side interface in **Hide** mode: on the left, the user selects a carrier and up to eight secret images (one per bit-plane, each with its own passphrase field and plane selector), with “Show/Copy” to handle passphrases; the blue action generates keys for empty fields, the green action applies keys and embeds, and the red action clears the session and revokes object URLs. On the right, the preview displays the generated stego image and offers “Download Stego Image”. All steps run locally in the browser (no network).

Operationally, we assume a trustworthy browser with minimal extensions, full-disk encryption on the workstation, careful disposal of originals and temporary files, attention to swap/paging, and session clearing after use. StegoCrypt does not claim resistance against advanced forensic steganalysis; the baseline adversary includes passive observers (histogram/noise checks) and active tampering [4, 6]. To validate fidelity, we compute MSE and PSNR for (i) cover vs. stego and (ii) original secret vs. extracted. Under a lossless pipeline (e.g., PNG/WebP lossless), extraction is bit-exact (MSE = 0, PSNR = ∞) for (ii). For (i), with single-bit-plane embedding and shuffled indices, preliminary runs indicate high visual quality (PSNR typically > 40 dB, content- and payload-dependent).

Overall, **StegoCrypt** contributes a practical multi-payload workflow with independent passphrases and strict separation between payload sealing (AES–GCM) and permutation generation (AES–CTR), along with an offline-by-default web implementation focused on security, performance, and usability.

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Figure 1. StegoCrypt, a browser-based system

References

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